

find information about Bethe's papers, correspondence, reports, etc. (pp. 312–313). From the history of science point of view, there are a few critical points. For instance, Hans Bethe in the chapter 'My life in astrophysics' (p. 34) mentions a rather absurd episode. 'Nobel's wife, he (Mr Rydberg of the Nobel Foundation) told me, had run-off with one of the leading mathematicians and astronomers of the time. So the Prize bequest had specified that the work honoured had to have practical application and that neither pure mathematics nor astronomy could be considered. Otherwise, Nobel feared, this man would have been one of the first winners'. However, historians of science have not been able to confirm such a story.

As the authors knew Hans Bethe personally (they were his friends, students and collaborators), it is understood that their views are subjective. Bethe has been presented as a man with no flaws.

The book is recommended for historians of science as well as scientists. It gives not only glimpses of Bethe's life, but also development of physics in the twentieth century.

RAJINDER SINGH

*University of Oldenburg,
Faculty V – Institute of Physics,
Research Group – Physics Education,
History and Philosophy of Science,
PO Box 2503,
26111 Oldenburg, Germany
e-mail: rajinder.singh@mail.uni-oldenburg.de*

The Atlas of Ideas: How Asian Innovation Can Benefit Us All. Charles Leadbeater and James Wisdon. Demos, Third Floor, 136 Tooley Street, London, UK, SE1 2TU, London. 2007. pp. 48. ISBN: 1

84180 174 7. Licensed under Creative Commons.

India: The Uneven Innovator. Kirsten Bound. Demos, London. 2007. pp. 64. ISBN: 1 84180 171 2. Licensed under Creative Commons.

China: The Next Science Superpower? James Wisdon and James Keeley. Demos, London. 2007. pp. 69. ISBN: 1 84180 173 9. Licensed under Creative Commons.

South Korea: Mass Innovation Comes of Age. Molly Webb. Demos, London. 2007. pp. 63. ISBN: 1 84180 171.0. Licensed under Creative Commons.

e-mail: hello@demos.co.uk; Cost of the pamphlets put together is British £40. Each costs £10. Electronic version is free to download under Creative Commons license.

It is difficult to believe that these four pamphlets with such abundance of data and insights have resulted from a mere 18-month study of science and innovation in Asia called *The Atlas of Ideas*.

The Demos team concludes rightly that the US and European pre-eminence in science-based innovation can no longer be taken for granted. Nor can the knowledge jobs that depended on it. The rise of China and India is sure to remake the innovation landscape. Every now and then, major newspapers and magazines report stories of incredible achievements from cities such as Shanghai, Beijing, Chongqing, Bangalore, Hyderabad, Chennai and Seoul. In a sense, this is similar to what happened in the mid-twentieth century, when the centre of gravity of science and innovation shifted from Europe to USA.

No doubt, both China and India face huge economic, social and environmental challenges, but both these nations believe that massive investments in science and technology can help them overcome these challenges. China has already

started making such massive investments and India is following suit. In India industry has acquired a new confidence, with leading Indian companies acquiring much larger companies elsewhere in the steel and aluminum sectors. Pharmaceutical companies have graduated from what the Western press used to describe as copycats to partnering in R&D with international pharma majors. Both the Indian and the Chinese economies are growing at a phenomenal rate. One hopes that the industry's growing sense of confidence soon rubs onto the scientific establishment in India. Unfortunately, say the authors, the Indian innovation system looks ramshackle and improvised.

South Korea's transformation from 'hermit kingdom' to a global technology power is truly dramatic. Compared to China and India, Korea is miniscule. However, the Koreans have shown phenomenal determination with their orderly innovation system consisting of the three policies of industrial techno-nationalism, scientific techno-nationalism, and ubiquitous innovation. Of late, Korea has started emphasizing on collaboration.

Demos believes that it is important for the United Kingdom to collaborate with these countries in research and innovation. Not just because of cost advantage, but because of a wider range of advantages.

The second phase of the *Atlas of Ideas* project will commence in April 2007.

These four pamphlets must be read by those involved in science policy making.

SUBBIAH ARUNACHALAM

*M.S. Swaminathan Research Foundation,
Third Cross Street,
Taramani Institutional Area,
Chennai 600 013, India
e-mail: subbiah.arunachalam@gmail.com*